

Intercropping In Mulberry Garden

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Introduction

Mulberry is a primary source of *Bombyx mori*. Particularly, mulberry silkworm has monophogas it can be depending on mulberry leaf. So, getting superior quality cocoon and silk mainly based on the mulberry leaf. Because of mulberry contains the entire nutritive content (Protein, moisture content, Vitamin, Carbohydrate etc.) are present. 70% of the silk produced by silkworm is directly derived from the protein of mulberry leaf.

Benefits of intercropping in mulberry garden

Mulberries can be raised in both irrigated and rainfed conditions. It is once planted; leaves can be given 12 to 15 years for the significantly. It continues for every variety because mulberry is a perennial plant and it is a tree pattern. There are several varieties of various characters for such variety is good yield and superior quality of leaf and rest upon the variety is good quality leaf but low yielding.

Several methods can be adopted for cultivation of mulberry in field conditions such as pit system, row system, paired row system etc. and the spacing for the row to row contains certain spacing that can be raised in some short duration crops which can be maintained for weed and additional income to farmers. The benefits of the intercropping hasten reduced the weed in the mulberry garden and increased the soil fertility and avoided soil erosion which can facilitate proper aeration in the soil. Intercropping crops for the mulberry garden like cow pea, green gram, black gram, Dhaincha, Sunhemp are essentially to raise garden which has improving soil fertility and producing good quality of mulberry leaf.

Dhaincha and Sunhemp are generally grown as a green manuring crop in India. It is a tall branching annual herb adapted to wet areas and heavy soils. For the green manure crops in mulberry garden which can be mulching at the 45th days using mechanization tools. In Dhaincha is for the crude protein content of seeds of *Sesbania* species is 33.0% and 10.9% crude fibre. It can also be used as fodder during the scarcity period. *Sesbania* species contain lectins.

Green manuring with leguminous crops like cowpea and horse gram can be practiced to increase the soil fertility. The seeds of green manuring crops @ 15 kg/ha/year can be broadcast taking advantages of monsoon when soil moisture is sufficiently high (Dandin *et al.* 2014)

Advantages of Green manure crops (Dhaincha) in mulberry garden

- Green manure crops are cover crops which can be covered in unwanted area in field condition.
- Minimized can be for the weed in useless areas for the crop's region.
- Intercrops can be helped for main crops in field site.
- Avoid soil erosion in cultivated field.
- Improved in soil quality and also enrich in topsoil
- It is legumes crops both plant and roots parts work with the bacteria top soil to trap nitrogen from the atmosphere.
- Enrich the soil with organic matter.
- Preventing leaching in soil.
- Suppressing for the weeds.
- Providing habitat for the natural predators
- Providing habitat for Pollinators
- Improving soil structure
- Support in natural microbes and soil organisms
- Menacing for pest life cycle and diseases

Dhaincha cultivation between the rows of Mulberry Garden

Reference

Dandin SB, Giridhar K. Handbook of sericulture technologies. Central Silk Board, Bangalore, India; 2014.